

Literature review regarding values, valuation and decision-making

Description of the searches performed

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The section is based on three types of processes for creating references:

- A. Those based on my expert knowledge.
- B. Those based on searches using search strings with general concepts
- C. Those based on searches using search strings based on more specific words or concepts. This latter kind of search would be based on the main issues as defined by the literature under A and B.

A. References based on my expert knowledge

This kind of references is a dominating source for the section. It is based on expertise obtained through 30 years of research within the field of environmental governance with an extensive number of publications – refereed journal articles and books by international and national publishers. Given the time frame for the values assessment, the kind of overview offered in the section would not have been possible without such a basis. This literature was used for two main purposes:

- To structure the presentation – decide on what issues and aspects would be included
- To help document more specific findings

B. Searches using search strings with general concepts

Different combinations of search terms like institutions, decision-making and values were used for these searches. These are broad concepts where it was difficult to narrow down the search to manageable numbers of references. I still wanted to do this kind of search to be more confident that my assessments based on sources under (A) did not have important gaps. This regards specifically point (A) above and the aim was in that respect to ensure that I had not missed important literature and hence foci.

This type of search actually gave few references that in the end were used. This may imply that the sources under (A) actually gave an adequate basis for defining what elements should be included in the assessment. However, the result may also be influenced by the difficulties faced with such broad terms. Below follows a documentation of the searches – all using Google Scholar as search engine and search words only in English. The engine was chosen to include also books, as books often have a broader perspective and function as documenting status in a specific field of research. The search was done in steps, typically narrowing down from ‘All years, wherever in the paper’ to ‘All years, only in headlines’ to ‘2010 and after’ mostly limited to ‘in headlines’. The first step (‘All years, wherever in the paper’) was typically done without any limitations. Then I went through a number of pages to see if there were any types of papers coming up that were irrelevant. As an example, a lot of the literature regarding ‘Institutions and decision-making’ regarded educational issues. As these were irrelevant, they were excluded. The documentation below shows the steps after this pre-stage was completed.

I did four searches following strategy B (a couple of searches are presented together as results overlapped):

Search 1:

1. Search terms: ‘Institutions’ and ‘decision-making’; not ‘education’, ‘educational’, ‘learning’

- All years (wherever in the text): 1 250 000. Not checked
- All years (only in headlines): 452. Checked the first 10 pages
- 2010 and after (only in headlines): 201 publications. Checked title of all (logically some overlap between the above)
- **Relevant documents found from search 1: 7**

This and later searches including the concept ‘institutions’ was impeded by the fact that many scholars use institutions synonymous with organizations, while the values assessment defines institutions as ‘rules’.

Searches 2 & 3:

2. Search terms: ‘Institutions’ and ‘environment’ and ‘environmental’ and ‘decision-making’; not ‘education’, ‘educational’, ‘learning’ (in the text)

- All years (wherever in the text): 459 000: Checked titles of all in first 10 pages
 - o Ikke i litteratur file
 - Obertür on Trade in Managing Institutional Complexity (Obertür and Stokke eds)
- 2010 and after (wherever in the text): 21 200. Checked 10 first pages
- 2010 and after (only in headlines and not using the term ‘environment’, only ‘environmental’): 3 hits, one relevant that was already found under the above

3. Search terms: ‘Institutions’ and ‘environment’ and ‘environmental’ and ‘decision-making’ and ‘a review’; not education, educational, learning, academic

- All years (only in titles): 170. All titles checked
Fant ikke noe om ble lasta ned, men burde se på Mees (2019): Sustainable Action and Motivation (bok)

Relevant documents found from searches 2 and 3: 17

Search 4:

4. Search terms: 'Values' and 'environment' and 'environmental' and 'decision-making':

- All years (wherever in the text): 2 820 000. Not checked
- 2010 and after (wherever in the text): 167 000. Checked 20 first pages
- All years (only in headlines, cutting 'environment'): 70. Checked all. Little of interest, several on individual level, mainly 'old'. Ordered Norton's book + a review of that book that came up.

Relevant documents found from search 4: 7 + 1 book

C. Searches using search strings based on more specific words or concepts

When writing the text, based on an outline defined by literatures under A and B, I got to specific topics where that literature was of little or no help. Hence, I made the following searches to complement (nine searches are presented in groups of two or three searches as results overlapped)

Searches 5 and 6:

5. Search terms: 'Modern agriculture' and 'environmental impacts'

- All: 2 400 000 hits. Did not check
- All from 2010: 18 300. Checked the first 10 pages
- All in title: 7 refs, all checked

6. Search terms: 'Modern agriculture' and 'pollution'

- All: 1 100 000 hits. Did not check
- All from 2010: 199 000. Checked the first 10 pages
- All in title: 5 refs, all checked

Relevant documents found from searches 5 and 6: 10

Searches 7, 8 and 9:

7. Search terms: 'Corporate' and 'decision-making'

- All: 2 880 000 hits. Did not check
- All from 2010: 1 550 000. Checked the first 10 pages
- All in title: 1200 refs, checked first 10 pages

8. Search terms: 'Corporate social responsibility' and 'decision-making'

- All: 2 450 000 hits. Did not check

- All from 2010: 66 800. Did not check
- All in title: 92 hits, checked all

9. Search term: 'Corporate social responsibility' (only)

- From 2010 only in titles: 20 700. Checked 10 first pages

Relevant documents found from searches 7, 8 and 9: 33

Search 10:

10. Search terms: 'Poverty' and 'deforestation'

- All: 145 000 hits. Did not check
- All from 2010: 37 200, checked 10 first pages
- All in title: 150 hits, checked all

Relevant documents found from search 10: 10

Search 11:

11. Search term 'greenwashing'

- All: 27 000 hits. Did not check
- All from 2010: 17 400 Did not check
- All in title: 1 030. Checked 10 first pages

Relevant documents found from search 11: 23

Search 12:

12. Search term 'values public policy'

- All: 3 040 000 hits. Brief check of first 20 pages - titles
- All from 2010: 17 400 Did not check
- All in title: 1 030. Checked 15 first pages

Relevant documents found from search 12: 18 (+1 book)

Searches 13 and 14:

13. Search term 'extractivist policies'

- All: 15 700 hits. Check of first 10 pages
- (All from 2010: 13 900 Did not check (note the small reduction, so most publications are from 2010 or later))

- All in title: 1. Checked

14. Search term 'extractivism, state, business'

- All: 17 700. check of first 10 pages
- All in title: None

Relevant documents found from searches 13 & 14: 27

Searches 15 & 16:

15. Search term 'economic growth as dominating goal'

- All: 8 720 hits. check of first 10 pages
- (All from 2010: 7 780 Did not check (note the small reduction, so most publ. are from 2010))
- All in title: None

16. Search term 'economic growth paradigm'

- All: 3 120 000 hits. Did not check
- All in title: 154. Checked the first 10 pages

Relevant documents found from searches 15 & 16: 11

Selection of fully read documents:

The assessment of what papers to read was based on the title and excerpts appearing in the results pages (thus, when stating that the first 10 results pages were checked, it implies that both the titles and the excerpts were read). Whenever these data seemed relevant, abstracts were read. Finally, full papers were read in case the abstract documented high relevance. Given the limited capacity to read all papers, only a limited number of them were fully read.

Some books were accessible via internet, while others had to be ordered.

During the writing process, some papers and books had to be revisited.

Altogether 163 papers were fully read, along with one book for Search 4 and one for search 12. It is likely that a couple of more books were consulted for different searches, but these were not documented.

The entire process allowed for there to be a good grasp of the evidence to inform the topics in section 2.4.2.3.